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Lip Print Patterns Among The Khasi Population Of Meghalaya: A Descriptive Study

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ABSTRACT

Lip prints are considered unique to each individual and may serve as a valuable tool in personal identification. Cheiloscopy, the study of lip groove patterns, is increasingly being explored in forensic investigation because of its individuality and persistence throughout life. The present study was conducted to evaluate the distribution of lip patterns among the Khasi population of Meghalaya, a tribal community with distinct anthropological characteristics. A total of 100 individuals (50 males and 50 females) participated in the study. Lip impressions were recorded using lipstick and cellophane tape and examined with the aid of magnification. The patterns were categorized according to the Suzuki and Tsuchihashi classification system. The analysis showed that Type IA was the most frequently observed pattern (37%), followed by Type IB (24%) and Type II (16%). A noticeable gender variation was identified, with Type IA occurring more commonly among females (22 cases), whereas males showed nearly equal prevalence of Type IA (15 cases) and Type IB (14 cases). These observations provide baseline cheiloscopy data for the Khasi population and highlight the possible role of lip prints as supportive evidence in forensic identification.

Keywords: Lip print, Identification, Khasi population, Cheiloscopy, Complete vertical groove.

INTRODUCTION

The pattern of grooves present on the vermilion portion of human lips is considered distinctive for each individual and has potential forensic relevance in establishing identity. The examination of these characteristics lip groove patterns is known as cheiloscopy. ⁽¹⁾The forensic significance of lip prints was first highlighted in the early twentieth century by R. Fischer, which initiated interest in their application in personal identification. ⁽²⁾

Previous studies conducted in different region of India have demonstrated that lip print patterns may vary across population, with certain types appearing more frequently within specific ethnic groups. For instance, studies by Vahanwalla and Parekh reported predominance of Type I patterns among female in a Mumbai based population. ⁽³⁾ Similarly, research by Sivapathasundharam and colleagues among Indo-Dravidian subjects observed a higher occurrence of Type III patterns. ⁽⁴⁾ Longitudinal observations by Coward RC indicated that lip groove configuration remains stable over time, reinforcing their usefulness in identification. ⁽⁵⁾ Further studies, including those by Gondivkar SM et al., suggested that lip prints may also assist sex determination. ⁽⁶⁾ Investigations conducted in the Kerala population by Verghese AJ and co-workers showed predominance of Type IV patterns in both sexes. ⁽⁷⁾

Collectively, these findings indicate that lip print patterns may demonstrate population-specific trends. The Khasi community of Meghalaya, belonging to the Austroasiatic linguistic lineage, represents a distinct ethnic group with unique anthropological features. However, limited information is available regarding their cheiloscopy characteristics. The present study was therefore undertaken to document the distribution of lip print patterns among the Khasi population and to evaluate possible gender related differences. Such data may contribute to strengthening the regional forensic database and expanding the practical relevance of cheiloscopy in identification procedure.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

1. To analyse lip print patterns among the Khasi population of Meghalaya.
2. To determine the most common lip print pattern within this population.
3. To compare and evaluate gender-wise differences in lip print patterns.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Lip prints were collected from 100 participants (50 males, 50 females) using a standardized method. Participants were asked to apply lipstick and then press their lips onto a piece of cello tape. The lip prints were then lifted using cello tape, which was gently pressed onto the tinted lip and then lifted off, transferring the print to the tape. The tape was then stuck onto a piece of paper for further analysis. Inclusion criteria were permanent residents of Meghalaya, aged 18-22 years, and belonging to the Khasi tribe. Exclusion criteria were individuals with lip deformities or injuries.

The lip prints were analyzed using a magnifying glass, and the patterns were classified into different types based on the presence and arrangement of lip grooves and fissures. Lip groove patterns were categorized according to the classification proposed by Suzuki and Tsuchihashi (1970)⁽⁸⁾ into the following types

- Type IA: Vertical grooves extending across the entire lip.
- Type IB: Vertical grooves covering only part of the lip.
- Type II: Branched groove pattern
- Type III: Intersected grooves
- Type IV: Reticular grooves
- Type V: Grooves that do not fit into types I–IV and remain unclassified.

RESULTS

The results showed that the most common lip print pattern among the Khasi population was Type I (37%), followed by Type II (24%), and Type III (16%).

TYPE	MALE	FEMALE	PERCENTAGE
IA	15	22	37%
IB	14	10	24%
II	9	7	16%
III	4	5	9%
IV	5	3	8%
V	3	3	6%

Type IA was the most prevalent pattern (37%), especially in females. Type IB was the second most common (24%), with higher occurrence in males. Gender differences were observed, suggesting potential sexual dimorphism in lip print distribution. Rare patterns included Type III, IV, and V

Fig1- Type IA: Vertical grooves extending across the entire lip.

Fig 2- Type IA: Vertical grooves extending across the entire lip.

Fig 3- Type IB: Vertical grooves covering only part of the lip

Intersected grooves

Fig 4- Type III:

DISCUSSION

The findings of the present study demonstrate that Type IA and IB are the most frequently observed lip print patterns among the Khasi population. Earlier studies conducted in different Indian population have reported varying dominant patterns. Vahanwalla and Parekh observed predominance of Type I patterns in their Mumbai-based sample which corresponds with the findings of the current study. ⁽³⁾In contrast, Sivapathasundharam and co-workers report Type III as the most common pattern among Ind-Dravidian subjects. ⁽⁴⁾Study conducted in the Kerala population by Verghese AJ et al. documented a higher frequency of Type IV patterns. ⁽⁷⁾

These variations suggest that lip print characteristics may differ among populations and ethnic groups. Such differences may have potential value in forensic identification and anthropological studies.

CONCLUSION

The present study indicates that Type IA is the most prevalent lip print pattern among the Khasi population of Meghalaya, followed by Type IB and Type II. Gender-based variation was also observed, with females showing a higher occurrence of Type IA, while males demonstrated a more even distribution between Types IA and IB.

Cheiloscopy continues to emerge as a supplementary tool in forensic identification due to the uniqueness and stability of lip groove patterns. The data generated from this study provide baseline information for the Khasi population and support the inclusion of lip print analysis in forensic investigations. Further research involving larger samples may help in strengthening its practical application in identification process.

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